

Assessing the effectiveness of Microfinance institutions on the growth and development of SMEs. A case study of Kalingalinga

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APA Citation and Referencing: Simubali, N., & Silwimba, P. (2025). Assessing the effectiveness of Microfinance institutions on the growth and development of SMEs. A case study of Kalingalinga. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 1(3), 906-922

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 24th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Microfinance SME Development Financial Inclusion Loan Accessibility Business Growth Zambia</p>	<p>This study examined the effectiveness of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) on the growth and development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kalingalinga using a Quantitative-method design, data was collected from 75 SMEs respondents through questionnaires. Primary data was collected and analyzed using Megastat. The findings reveal a significant association between the ease of accessing credit from MFIs and the accessibility of microfinance services to businesses. Among respondents who found it very difficult to access credit, 12 rated accessibilities as very poor and 6 rated it as poor. In contrast, among those who found it easy to access credit, 5 rated accessibilities as good. The chi-square test confirms a statistically significant association between the two variables ($X^2 = 124.35$, $df = 16$, $p\text{-value} = 0.00$), indicating that respondents who found it easier to access credit also tended to rate the accessibility of microfinance services more favorably. The study has also used the hypothesis test in evaluating whether the mean extent of MFI support contributing to business growth is significantly different from a hypothesized value of 3.000, which represents a moderate extent of contribution. The sample mean is 3.307, indicating that, on average, respondents reported a slightly higher than moderate extent of contribution. The standard deviation is 1.230, and the standard error is 0.142. With a sample size of 75 and 74 degrees of freedom, the t-statistic is 2.16, and the p-value is 0.0341 (two-tailed). This indicates that the mean extent of MFI support contributing to business growth is significantly different from the hypothesized value of 3.000 at a 5% significance level. Furthermore, the study shows that the regression analysis examines the relationship between the challenges faced with repayment of MFI loans and independent variables like Number of Employees. The R^2 value of 0.556 indicates that approximately 55.6% of the variation in repayment challenges can be explained by the three independent variables. The Adjusted R^2 value of 0.537 suggests that the model is moderately robust. Recommendations are proposed: MFIs should reconsider their loan terms, MFIs should review their interest rates, repayment schedules, and loan sizes to make their services more accessible and manageable for borrowers. Invest in financial literacy programs, MFIs should invest in financial literacy programs.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Small, and medium enterprises (SMEs) are widely acknowledged as key drivers of economic development, employment creation, and poverty alleviation, particularly in developing economies. According to the World Bank (2022), SMEs account for about 90% of businesses and more than 50% of employment worldwide. Their contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and innovation has increasingly positioned them at the heart of national development strategies. Despite their potential, many SMEs face persistent financial constraints that limit their ability to grow and operate effectively. This has led to the emergence of microfinance institutions (MFIs) as critical instruments for financial inclusion and business empowerment.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite the increasing presence of microfinance institutions in Zambia, many SMEs in peri-urban areas such as Kalingalinga continue to struggle with financial constraints, limited capacity, and business stagnation. While MFIs are designed to provide

much-needed financial support to underserved entrepreneurs, their actual effectiveness in fostering SME growth remains under-researched, particularly at the local level.

Some studies (e.g., Chikumbi, 2020; Musona & Phiri, 2019) have suggested that while microfinance services improve access to credit, they do not always translate into business expansion or long-term development. Issues such as high interest rates, lack of financial literacy, inadequate loan sizes, and poor repayment terms continue to hamper the success of microfinance beneficiaries. Moreover, in local communities like Kalingalinga, there is little empirical evidence on how SMEs utilize microfinance services and whether these services truly contribute to improved business outcomes.

1.3 Research Objectives

The general and specific objectives of this study are presented in the sections below.

1.3.1 General Objectives

The main objective of this study is to assess the effectiveness of microfinance institutions on the growth and development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Kalingalinga Compound, Lusaka.

Specific Objectives:

1. To assess the accessibility and utilization of microfinance services to SMEs in Kalingalinga.
2. To examine microfinance financial institutions impact on the growth of SMEs.
3. To identify the key challenges and determine the extent to which Microfinance institutions contributes to SMEs outcomes in terms of revenue growth, job creation, and business expansion.

1.3.2 Research Questions

1. To what extent are microfinance services accessible and utilized by SMEs in Kalingalinga?
2. What impact do microfinance institutions have on the growth and development of SMEs in Kalingalinga?
3. What key challenges do SMEs face in accessing microfinance services, and how do these services influence outcomes such as revenue growth, job creation, and business expansion?

1.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between microfinance services (independent variable) and the growth and development of SMEs (dependent variable), with moderating variables such as financial literacy, regulatory environment, and business management skills influencing the effectiveness of microfinance interventions. This framework is aligned with the study objectives and reflects the core themes guiding the research.

Figure 1.1: Conceptual framework

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study is significant for several stakeholders, including policymakers, microfinance institutions, SMEs owners, and researchers. Firstly, for policymakers and regulatory authorities such as the Bank of Zambia and the Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprise Development, the findings will provide empirical evidence necessary to guide policy formulation aimed at enhancing financial inclusion and SME support mechanisms.

Secondly, for microfinance institutions operating in Lusaka and similar communities, the study will offer insights into how their services are perceived and utilized by local SMEs, enabling them to tailor their financial products to meet the real needs of entrepreneurs. This could result in improved service delivery, greater client retention, and enhanced impact.

Thirdly, SMEs owners in Kalingalinga will benefit from the research by gaining a clearer understanding of the opportunities and pitfalls of microfinance. The study will highlight success stories and challenges that other businesses in similar circumstances can learn from, thereby improving business practices and financial decision-making.

Lastly, for academic researchers and development practitioners, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on microfinance and SMEs development in Zambia. It helps fill a local-level knowledge gap by focusing on a community that has received little empirical attention, thus offering a context-specific perspective to broader development discussions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Accessibility and Utilization of Microfinance Services by SMEs

Globally, microfinance has emerged as a pivotal instrument for improving access to financial services among underserved populations, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The primary objective of microfinance is to provide small-scale financial services such as credit, savings, insurance, and payment systems to individuals and businesses excluded from the formal banking sector (Ledgerwood, 2013; Hermes & Lensink, 2011). Microfinance institutions (MFIs) have evolved as catalysts of inclusive finance, designed to bridge the financial accessibility gap for entrepreneurs who often lack collateral, credit history, or formal employment records. This model has gained momentum as a strategic pathway for empowering low-income entrepreneurs, fostering financial inclusion, and enhancing local economic development (Cull et al., 2009; Churchill & Frankiewicz, 2006).

Third, gender disparities continue to shape microfinance outcomes across the region. These insights point to the need for more context-specific approaches in microfinance program design. Policymakers and practitioners must account for local economic conditions, cultural norms, and infrastructure realities when developing financial inclusion strategies (Sinha, 2005; Jack & Suri, 2011). Tailored interventions such as mobile training programs, group lending schemes, and credit guarantee facilities can help bridge the gap between supply and demand in the microfinance sector.

Despite these efforts, the gap between the theoretical accessibility of MFIs and actual utilization on the ground remains substantial. Tembo and Mulenga (2019) concluded that there is a critical need for more inclusive and targeted outreach efforts by MFIs operating in marginalized communities like Kalingalinga, Chibolya, and Kanyama. Without meaningful engagement, trust-building, and simplification of procedures, many SMEs will continue to rely on informal financial systems that, while helpful, may not provide the capital required for long-term business growth.

2.2 Impact of Microfinance on SME Growth and Development

The global experience with microfinance demonstrates varied impacts on the growth and development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). While microfinance is widely recognized as a tool to bridge financial gaps and promote entrepreneurship, its effects on SMEs growth are dependent on the structure of the programs, the local economic environment, and the characteristics of the targeted businesses. Numerous studies across different regions have illustrated both the potential and limitations of microfinance in enhancing SMEs performance.

Armendáriz and Morduch (2010) conducted one of the most influential meta-analyses in this field. Their research synthesized findings from various global studies and concluded that microfinance has a generally positive impact on SMEs development, especially in terms of asset accumulation, job creation, and business sustainability. In Bangladesh, where microfinance has been extensively promoted by institutions such as Grameen Bank and BRAC, SMEs supported by microfinance showed higher survival rates and improvements in household consumption and education outcomes. These outcomes underscore the broader socio-economic benefits of microfinance beyond mere enterprise growth.

However, the effectiveness of microfinance is not universally guaranteed. Banerjee et al. (2015), in a series of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) conducted in Hyderabad, India, found more nuanced results. Their study involved over 6,000 households and evaluated the long-term impact of access to microcredit. The results indicated that while access to microfinance led to a significant increase in the number of new businesses and some expansion of existing enterprises, the overall effect on average profits and consumption was modest. Not all SMEs experienced sustained growth after receiving loans, and many reverted to their pre-loan levels of operation once the funds were exhausted. These findings suggest that microfinance alone may not be sufficient to drive long-term enterprise success and must be complemented with business development services such as training and mentorship.

Initiatives such as the SANAD Fund for MSMEs have attempted to address these barriers by offering gender-sensitive products and supporting capacity-building programs.

From a theoretical standpoint, the Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firm can help explain the variable impact of microfinance on SME growth. According to Barney (1991), firms grow by acquiring and effectively utilizing valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources. Microfinance provides SMEs with financial capital, a necessary but not sufficient condition for sustainable growth. Without complementary resources such as skilled labor, managerial capacity, and access to markets, the infusion of capital may not yield substantial or lasting benefits.

Moreover, behavioral economics offers insights into how SME owners make financial decisions once they receive microfinance. Research by Duflo and Kremer (2011) shows that entrepreneurs often engage in suboptimal spending behaviors due to lack of financial planning skills or external pressures. This observation reinforces the need for integrating financial literacy training with microfinance programs to ensure that funds are utilized effectively and that borrowers can navigate the complexities of credit management.

Technological innovation has emerged as a key enabler of microfinance effectiveness in recent years. Mobile money platforms and digital lending services have made it easier for SMEs to access credit, particularly in regions with low banking infrastructure. A World Bank (2022) report indicated that digital microfinance services increased SMEs loan uptake by 25% in countries like Kenya, the Philippines, and India. These platforms offer real-time credit scoring, reduced transaction costs, and improved transparency, all of which contribute to better loan utilization and business growth.

However, these digital innovations also introduce new challenges. According to Chen and Rasmussen (2019), reliance on automated credit scoring can inadvertently exclude businesses with non-traditional credit profiles, such as seasonal vendors and informal traders. Furthermore, concerns about data privacy and digital literacy must be addressed to ensure inclusive access.

In high-income countries, microfinance is typically targeted at specific vulnerable groups, such as immigrants, youth, and women. In the United States, organizations like Accion and the Opportunity Fund provide microloans to underserved entrepreneurs. A study by Servon (2017) found that such programs led to increased business formalization, improved credit scores, and higher income stability for recipients. While the scale of impact may be smaller compared to developing countries, the underlying principle remains the same: microfinance can be a catalyst for SME growth when delivered in a supportive and enabling environment.

In Zambia, where a large portion of SMEs operates in the informal sector, the inability to provide adequate collateral is a frequent challenge. Tembo and Mulenga (2019) similarly found that a lack of collateral was one of the primary reasons why SMEs in informal settlements struggled to access formal credit, including microfinance loans. This highlights the need for MFIs to adopt more flexible lending criteria, taking into account the socio-economic realities of the borrowers and their businesses. Microfinance institutions that require formal documentation or tangible collateral often exclude a significant number of small enterprises from the credit market, exacerbating financial exclusion.

Financial literacy is another critical factor affecting the effectiveness of microfinance in Zambia. Mwansa and Phiri (2018) found that many SMEs owners in Ndola lacked the necessary skills to manage business finances, including budgeting, debt management, and investment planning. This lack of financial literacy contributed to poor decision-making and, in some cases, business failure despite receiving loans. The authors suggested that financial education should be incorporated as part of the loan process, alongside the provision of business development services (BDS) such as bookkeeping support, marketing, and networking opportunities.

Furthermore, the role of entrepreneurship skills in determining the success of microfinance interventions cannot be overstated. Studies by Chikumbi (2020) and Banda (2021) have shown that SMEs in Zambia often struggle with the day-to-day management of their businesses, including customer relations, supply chain management, and pricing strategies. Providing targeted training in entrepreneurship, in addition to access to credit, has been shown to significantly improve the performance of SMEs. This is corroborated by global findings such as those by Coleman (2007), who found that microfinance interventions that were accompanied by entrepreneurship training had more sustainable results in terms of business growth and job creation.

The findings of these studies suggest that microfinance in Zambia should be viewed not only as a source of capital but also as a vehicle for broader socio-economic empowerment. To achieve sustainable business growth, microfinance programs must be designed as comprehensive support systems that offer financial resources alongside capacity-building initiatives. This holistic approach is supported by scholars such as Christen et al. (2004), who argue that financial services, when combined with education and training, are more likely to have a positive impact on the long-term growth and sustainability of SMEs.

In line with this, the Bank of Zambia (2023) has recommended that MFIs operating in Zambia implement programs that focus on both the financial and non-financial needs of SMEs. Such initiatives might include financial literacy campaigns, management training, and access to market information. Moreover, the Bank of Zambia has called for greater collaboration between MFIs, government agencies, and development partners to create an enabling environment for SMEs. This includes improving the regulatory framework to ensure that MFIs operate in a transparent and accountable manner and that borrowers have adequate protection against predatory lending practices.

Several policy recommendations can be drawn from the findings of these studies. First, it is essential for the Zambian government to create a conducive environment for microfinance institutions to operate effectively. This involves enhancing the regulatory framework for microfinance, ensuring that MFIs are held accountable for fair lending practices, and promoting transparency in the lending process. The government should also provide incentives for MFIs that offer low-interest rates, flexible repayment terms, and support services such as financial literacy training.

Second, MFIs in Zambia should focus on developing more flexible lending products that are tailored to the unique needs of SMEs, particularly in the informal sector. These products should consider the cash flow cycles of SMEs, which can be irregular, and allow for more flexible repayment schedules. Additionally, MFIs should explore innovative solutions such as digital lending platforms, which can reduce the cost of loan processing and expand access to credit for SMEs in remote areas.

Third, the Zambian government and MFIs should collaborate on creating a robust national framework for financial education. Integrating financial literacy into school curriculums and offering training programs for adult entrepreneurs would help to equip business owners with the knowledge and skills needed to manage their finances effectively.

Finally, policymakers should foster stronger linkages between microfinance institutions, business development services, and other forms of financial support, including access to venture capital and trade finance. Such integrated support would increase the likelihood of business survival and growth, particularly for small businesses in high-risk sectors.

The evidence from Zambia suggests that microfinance can play a crucial role in promoting SME growth, particularly by enhancing access to capital. However, the effectiveness of microfinance in Zambia is contingent upon a variety of factors, including financial literacy, loan terms, and the broader business environment. To unlock the full potential of microfinance, policymakers, MFIs, and development partners must adopt a more integrated approach that combines financial services with

entrepreneurship training and capacity-building initiatives. This would provide SMEs with the tools they need not only to survive but to thrive in an increasingly competitive market environment.

2.3 Challenges and Perceptions Regarding Microfinance Services

Borrower perceptions of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) are critical in assessing the efficacy and sustainability of microfinance programs globally. These perceptions are shaped by various factors, including service delivery quality, interest rates, transparency, customer relations, and the socio-economic context of borrowers. Understanding these perceptions provides valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of microfinance initiatives across different regions.

Borrower perceptions of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) in Zambia are shaped by a complex interplay of factors, including accessibility, interest rates, repayment terms, and service delivery. Understanding these perceptions is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of microfinance initiatives and identifying areas for improvement.

In Zambia, many Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SMEs) owners perceive MFIs as more accessible compared to traditional commercial banks. Musona and Kabwe (2022) found that SME owners in Lusaka appreciated the relative ease of obtaining loans from MFIs, citing fewer bureaucratic hurdles and more flexible requirements. However, this accessibility often comes with trade-offs, as borrowers expressed dissatisfaction with high interest rates and rigid repayment schedules.

Similarly, in Kalingalinga, Banda (2021) reported that clients experienced a mix of gratitude and anxiety grateful for the access to credit but anxious about the repayment obligations and interest rates. This duality underscores the complex relationship borrowers have with MFIs, where the immediate benefits of access are tempered by concerns over long-term financial sustainability.

High interest rates and inflexible repayment terms are recurring concerns among microfinance clients in Zambia. Kubansa (2025) conducted a study in Chongwe District, Lusaka Province, revealing that while MFIs play a significant role in providing financial services to farmers, high-interest rates and stringent loan requirements impede their potential contribution to poverty reduction. The study concluded that for MFIs to be more effective in poverty alleviation, there needs to be a review of interest rates, repayment terms, and loan requirements, and a stronger emphasis on developing tailored financial products that meet the specific needs of farmers. Moreover, Kamanga (2025) highlighted that effective credit risk management practices, such as thorough evaluation of business plans and continuous monitoring, are essential in reducing default rates and enhancing loan performance. The study emphasized that professionalism in borrower assessment and enhanced project monitoring mechanisms are crucial for improving loan repayment rates and overall borrower satisfaction.

The role of loan officers is pivotal in shaping borrower perceptions. Siwale (2016) examined the experiences of loan officers in Zambia, revealing that social expectations and cultural norms significantly influence their interactions with clients. The study found that female loan officers often faced greater challenges due to societal pressures, impacting their ability to effectively manage client relationships. These dynamics can affect the overall client experience and perception of MFIs.

Microfinance has the potential to improve living standards, but its effectiveness is contingent on various factors. Banda (2010) conducted a study in Chipata District, Eastern Province, assessing the effects of microfinance loans on sustaining improvements in beneficiaries' living standards. The study found that while initial loan access led to some improvements, the lack of sustainability strategies and inadequate support mechanisms limited long-term benefits. The research recommended that MFIs facilitate start-up and refresher trainings, monitor beneficiary selection, and establish linkages with commercial lending institutions and markets to enhance sustainability.

Furthermore, the MicroLoan Foundation's initiatives in Zambia have demonstrated the positive impact of microfinance on women's empowerment and community development. By providing small loans and business training to economically disadvantaged women, the foundation has enabled many to start and grow businesses, leading to improved household incomes and investments in education, health, and nutrition. The high repayment rates and successive borrowing cycles indicate a strong commitment among clients and the potential for microfinance to drive community-level change.

Loan defaults remain a significant challenge for MFIs in Zambia. Zulu et al. (2024) investigated the impact of loan defaults on the profitability of MFIs, identifying poor credit assessment, lack of loan monitoring, and inadequate recovery measures as key contributors to non-performing loans. The study also noted that external factors, such as economic downturns and events like the COVID-19 pandemic, exacerbate default rates. To mitigate these issues, the research recommended suspending loan disbursements during natural disasters, implementing consistent monitoring, and enhancing credit evaluation processes.

Financial literacy is another critical factor influencing borrower perceptions and repayment behavior. Limited understanding of financial products and services can lead to misinformed borrowing decisions and increased default risks. Enhancing financial education among clients is essential for improving loan utilization and repayment outcomes.

Borrower perceptions of MFIs in Zambia are multifaceted, reflecting a balance between the appreciation of accessible financial services and concerns over high interest rates, rigid repayment terms, and cultural dynamics in service delivery. Addressing these issues requires a holistic approach, including reviewing loan terms, enhancing credit risk management practices, providing financial literacy education, and adopting culturally sensitive service delivery.

3. Methodology

This outlines the research methodology adopted for It provides a comprehensive explanation of the research design, target population, sampling design, data collection methods, sample size determination and data analysis techniques. Additionally, it discusses the triangulation approach, limitations of the study, and ethical considerations to ensure the reliability, validity, and integrity of the research.

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative-method research design approaches to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. The quantitative component involves the use of questionnaires to collect data on access, utilization, and impact of microfinance services of SMEs owners. This design is appropriate as it allows for statistical generalization. It also supports triangulation, thereby improving the reliability and validity of the findings.

3.1.2 Target Population

The target population for this study comprises small and medium enterprise (SMEs) owners and operators in Kalingalinga Compound, as well as officials from selected microfinance institutions (MFIs) operating in the area. SMEs within this community are typically involved in trade, manufacturing, services, and informal enterprises. The estimated number of SMEs in Kalingalinga is about 500, according to the Lusaka City Council business registry (2024).

3.1.3 Sampling Design

The study employs a random sampling technique for selecting SMEs respondents. The population is divided into based on business types (e.g., trade, manufacturing, services), from which a random sample is drawn. This ensures that various categories of SMEs are proportionately represented. This allows the researcher to obtain rich, in-depth data from individuals who are directly involved in or knowledgeable about microfinance and SMEs development.

3.1.4 Data Collection Methods

Primary data will be collected using questionnaires for SMEs respondents. The questionnaire will include both closed-ended and Likert-scale items to assess usage and outcomes of microfinance services. Data collection will be conducted in person, and instruments will be pre-tested in a pilot study to ensure clarity and reliability. Secondary data from institutional reports and academic literature will also support the study.

3.2 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study is determined using the appropriate known population size: sample size 75, Therefore, the study will involve a rounded off figure of 75 SMEs participants for the quantitative component.

3.2.1 Data Collection Methods

Primary data will be collected using questionnaires for SMEs respondents. The questionnaire will include both closed-ended and Likert-scale items to assess usage and outcomes of microfinance services. Data collection will be conducted in person, and instruments will be pre-tested in a pilot study to ensure clarity and reliability. Secondary data from institutional reports and academic literature will also support the study.

3.2.2 Data Analysis

The study will employ quantitative data analysis techniques Quantitative data from questionnaires will be coded and analyzed. Descriptive statistics (mean, frequency, percentages) and inferential statistics (correlation and regression) will be used to examine relationships between variables.

3.2.3 Triangulation

To enhance the validity and reliability of the research findings, triangulation will be used by integrating data from multiple sources quantitative surveys, and document review. Triangulation allows the researcher to cross-verify information and identify consistent patterns across data sets. It also reduces bias and enriches the interpretation of results. By comparing responses from SMEs owners with those of MFIs officials and cross-referencing with institutional records, the study gains a more nuanced and credible perspective on the effectiveness of microfinance services.

3.2.4 Limitations of the Study

The study is subject to several limitations. First, the findings may not be generalizable beyond Kalingalinga Compound, although they may provide indicative insights for similar peri-urban communities. Secondly, some SME owners may be unwilling to disclose sensitive financial information, which could affect the accuracy of self-reported data. Thirdly, time and resource constraints may limit the extent of fieldwork and data collection. Nonetheless, efforts will be made to mitigate these issues by ensuring respondent confidentiality and using validated instruments.

3.2.5 Ethical Considerations

The study adheres to ethical principles to ensure the integrity and respect of all participants.

4. Research Results

This chapter presents the findings of the study per thematic area which are in tables and graphs. Furthermore, the chapter discussed the research findings of this study. The main purpose of the study was to assess the effectiveness of microfinance on the growth and development of SMEs in Kalingalinga. This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section begins by giving background information of the respondents while the second part is a presentation and the third part discusses the research findings in relation to the research objectives of the study.

4.1 Demographic information

4.1.1 Cross Tabulation Between Age and Gender

Table 4.1 Below is a cross distribution of respondents according to age and gender

Table 4.1 Age and Gender

Age of Respondents	Gender:		Total
	Male	Female	
Below 20 years	0	0	0
21-30 year	6	5	11
31-40 years	16	5	21
41-50 year	10	16	26
Above 50 years	17	0	17
Total	49	26	75

The cross-tabulation in table 4.1 above shows the distribution of respondents by age and gender. Out of the 75 respondents, 49 (65%) are male and 26 (35%) are female. The majority of respondents (26, 35%) fall within the 41-50 years' age range, followed by those above 50 years (17, 23%), and 31-40 years (21, 28%). While, there was no respondents below 20 years. In terms of gender distribution, males dominate the 31-40 years 16 respondents, representing 33% and above 50 years were 17 respondents representing 35% age ranges, while females were more represented in the 41-50 years' age range with 16 respondents representing 62%. The 21-30 years' age range had a relatively balanced gender distribution with 6 males, and 5 females. Overall, the data suggests an older demographic, with most respondents being male and between 41-50 years old.

4.1.2 Marital Status

Figure 4.1 Below is the representation of respondents according to Marital Status

Figure 4.1 Marital Status

The data shows that the majority of respondents, 57.3%, were married, indicating a significant proportion of the sample are in a committed relationship. A substantial number, of 36%, indicated single, suggesting a considerable portion of the sample yet to enter into marriage. A small percentage 6.7% were divorced, indicating a relatively low incidence of marital dissolution. Notably, there are no widowed respondents in the sample, which may suggest that the sample is relatively young or that widowed individuals are underrepresented. Overall, the data suggests a predominantly married population with a significant minority of single individuals.

4.1.3 Level of Education

Figure 4.2 Below is the distribution of respondents according to level of education.

Figure 4.2 Level of Education

The data in figure 4.2 above, reveals that the majority of respondents, 37.3%, have completed secondary education, indicating a significant proportion of the sample has attained a moderate level of education. Followed by 22.7%, who did only primary education, while 20% have vocational or skills training. Only 13.3% respondents had tertiary education, suggesting a relatively low level of higher education attainment. Furthermore, 6.7% respondents had no formal education, highlighting a small but significant minority with limited educational background. Overall, the data suggests a predominantly secondary-educated population with a notable proportion having primary or vocational education.

4.2 To assess the accessibility and utilization of microfinance services to SMEs in Kalingalinga.

4.2.1 Number of Employees

Figure 4.3 Below is a representation of respondents according their number of employees

Figure 4.3 Number of Employees

The data reveals that the majority of respondents, 40% (30), have more than 10 employees, indicating a significant proportion of businesses with a substantial workforce. A notable 28% (21) have 6-10 employees, while 24% (18) have 1-5 employees, suggesting a mix of small and medium-sized enterprises. Only 8% (6) of respondents are self-employed with no employees, indicating a relatively low number of solo entrepreneurs. Overall, the data suggests that most businesses in the sample are established with a sizable workforce, with a significant proportion having more than 10 employees.

4.2.2 How easy is it to access credit from MFIs

Figure 4.4 Shows the distribution of responses when respondents were asked to state how easy is it to access credit from MFIs

Figure 4.4 Access to credit from MFIs

The data reveals that accessing credit from Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) was a challenging process for many respondents. A significant 46.7% (35 respondents) find it either difficult (22.7%) or very difficult (24%) to access credit, indicating a substantial barrier to financial resources. In contrast, only 20% (15 respondents) find it easy (13.3%) or very easy (6.7%) to access credit, suggesting that MFIs may have stringent requirements or processes that deter potential borrowers. The majority, 33.3% (25 respondents), perceive the process as moderate, indicating a neutral or middle-ground stance. Overall, the data suggests that accessing credit from MFIs is a significant challenge for many respondents.

4.2.3 Cross Tabulation Between Denied a Loan by an MFI and The Main Reason for Denied

Figure 4.5 Below shows the responses when respondents were asked to state whether they consider interest rates charged by MFIs affordable.

Figure 4.5 Do you consider Interest charged by MFIs

The data shows that a significant majority, 85.3% (64 respondents), consider the interest rates charged by MFIs affordable, indicating a high level of satisfaction with the rates. In contrast, only 14.7% (11 respondents) find the interest rates unaffordable, suggesting that MFIs are generally meeting the financial needs of their clients at acceptable costs. Overall, the data suggests that the interest rates charged by MFIs are generally considered affordable by the vast majority of respondents.

4.2.4 How often do you access loans from MFIs

The respondents were asked to indicate how often do they access loan from MFIs, the results are shown in figure 4.6 below

Figure 4.6 How often do you access loans from MFIs

The data shows that the majority of respondents, 62.7% (47 respondents), access financial training from MFIs, indicating a strong interest in capacity building and financial literacy. A notable 13.3% (10 respondents) access loan services, suggesting that some respondents are utilizing MFI credit facilities. However, 24% (18 respondents) do not access any services, indicating a significant proportion of respondents may not be utilizing MFI services. Surprisingly, no respondents reported accessing savings facilities or business development support, highlighting potential gaps in MFI service offerings.

Table 4.2 Below shows the chi-square results between Access to Credit and Accessibility of Microfinance Services

Table 4.2 A chi-square test

How easy is it to access credit from MFIs	How would you rate the accessibility of microfinance services to your business?					Total
	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Very poor	
Very easy	0	0	5	0	0	5
Easy	0	5	0	0	0	10
Moderate	0	10	15	0	0	25
Difficult	5	0	0	12	0	17
Very difficult	0	0	0	6	12	18
Total	5	15	20	23	12	75

124.35 chi-square
16 df
0.00 p-value

The cross-tabulation reveals a significant association between the ease of accessing credit from MFIs and the accessibility of microfinance services to businesses. Among respondents who found it very difficult to access credit, 12 rated accessibility as very poor and 6 rated it as poor. In contrast, among those who found it easy to access credit, 5 rated accessibility as good. The chi-square test confirms a statistically significant association between the two variables ($X^2 = 124.35$, $df = 16$, $p\text{-value} = 0.00$), indicating that respondents who found it easier to access credit also tended to rate the accessibility of microfinance services more favorably.

The data suggests that improving the ease of accessing credit from MFIs could lead to better perceptions of microfinance service accessibility among businesses. The strong association between these variables highlights the importance of streamlining credit access processes to enhance overall accessibility.

4.3 To examine microfinance financial institutions impact on the growth of SMEs

4.3.1 Business growth as result of Accessing Microfinance Services

The respondents were asked to state whether their businesses grown since they started accessing microfinance. The following results are shown on figure 4.7 below.

Figure 4.7 Business growth as result of Accessing Microfinance Services

The data in figure 4.7 above, shows that 53.3% (40 respondents) reported that their business has grown since accessing microfinance services, indicating a positive impact of these services on business growth. However, 46.7% (35 respondents) reported no growth, suggesting that microfinance services may not be having the desired effect for a significant proportion of respondents.

4.3.10 A significant hypothesis test; Mean vs Hypothesized

The table shows the hypothesis test using mean vs hypothesized. The results are shown below in table 4.8 below.

Table 4.3 Mean vs Hypothesized

Hypothesis Test: Mean vs. Hypothesized Value	
3.000	hypothesized value
	mean To what extent has MFI support contributed to your business growth
3.307	
1.230	std. dev.
0.142	std. error
75	n
74	df
2.16	t
.0341	p-value (two-tailed)

The hypothesis test is evaluating whether the mean extent of MFI support contributing to business growth is significantly different from a hypothesized value of 3.000, which represents a moderate extent of contribution. The sample mean is 3.307, indicating

that, on average, respondents reported a slightly higher than moderate extent of contribution. The standard deviation is 1.230, and the standard error is 0.142. With a sample size of 75 and 74 degrees of freedom, the t-statistic is 2.16, and the p-value is 0.0341 (two-tailed). This indicates that the mean extent of MFI support contributing to business growth is significantly different from the hypothesized value of 3.000 at a 5% significance level. In other words, the data suggests that MFI support has contributed to business growth to an extent that is statistically significantly higher than moderate.

4.4 The key challenges and the extent to which Microfinance institutions contributes to SMEs outcomes in terms of revenue growth, job creation, and business expansion.

4.4.1 What challenges do you face with repayment of MFI loans?

Figure 4.8 Below shows the challenges faced with repayment of MFIs loan.

Figure 4.8 What challenges do you face with repayment of MFI loans

The data reveals that respondents face various challenges with repayment of MFI loans, with the most significant being high interest rates, reported by 37.3% (28 respondents). Short repayment periods and small loan size are also major concerns, each affecting 21.3% (16 respondents) of respondents. Additionally, 20% (15 respondents) cited penalties for late payment as a challenge. These findings suggest that MFIs may need to reconsider their loan terms, including interest rates and repayment schedules, to make their services more accessible and manageable for borrowers.

4.4.2 How would you rate the repayment terms offered by MFIs

The respondents were asked to state to rate the MFIs repayment terms offered by MFIs, the following responses below in figure 4.9 Below

Figure 4.9 How would you rate the repayment terms offered by MFIs

The data shows that 33.3% (25 respondents) rate the repayment terms offered by MFIs as favorable (13.3%) or very favorable (20%), indicating a relatively positive perception. A significant proportion, 42.7% (32 respondents), are neutral, suggesting they may not have strong feelings either way or may be undecided. However, 24% (18 respondents) rate the repayment terms as unfavorable (16%) or very unfavorable (8%), indicating a notable level of dissatisfaction. Overall, the data suggests that while some respondents appreciate the repayment terms, there is room for improvement to make MFI services more appealing to a broader range of clients.

4.4.3 To what extent do MFIs contribute to job creation in your business

Figure 4.10 below shows the responses when respondents were asked whether MFIs contribute to job creation.

Figure 4.10 extent do MFIs contribute to job creation in your business

MFIs are perceived to contribute to job creation in businesses to a varying extent. About 40% (30 respondents) reported a high (13.3%) or very high (26.7%) contribution, indicating a positive impact on employment. A further 29.3% (22 respondents) reported a moderate contribution. However, 30.7% (23 respondents) reported a low (14.7%) or very low (16%) contribution, suggesting that MFIs may not be playing a significant role in job creation for a substantial proportion of respondents.

4.4.4 Do you believe MFI services are sustainable for SMEs in the long run

Figure 4.11 Do you believe MFI services are sustainable for SMEs in the long run

A significant majority, 60% (45 respondents), believe MFI services are sustainable for SMEs in the long run, with 30.7% (23 respondents) strongly agreeing and 29.3% (22 respondents) agreeing. A further 26.7% (20 respondents) are neutral, while a minority of 13.4% (10 respondents) disagree or strongly disagree, indicating some concerns about long-term sustainability. Overall, the data suggests that most respondents have a positive outlook on the sustainability of MFI services for SMEs.

13 Regression Analysis test

Table 4.4 Regression Analysis

Regression Analysis						
	R ²	0.556				
	Adjusted					
	R ²	0.537	n	75		
	R	0.745	k	3		
	Std. Error	0.790	Dep. Var.	What challenges do you face with repayment of MFI loans?		
ANOVA table						
Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	
Regression	55.3888	3	18.4629	29.60	0.00	
Residual	44.2912	71	0.6238			
Total	99.6800	74				
Regression output						
variables	coefficient	std. error	t (df=71)	p-value	confidence interval	
Intercept	0.1857	0.3013	0.616	.5396	-0.4151	0.7865
Type of Business	-1.0043	0.1608	-6.245	0.00	-1.3249	-0.6836
Period in Business	1.2215	0.1644	7.432	0.00	0.8938	1.5492
Number of Employees	-0.1169	0.1513	-0.773	.4424	-0.4187	0.1849

The regression analysis examines the relationship between the challenges faced with repayment of MFI loans and three independent variables: Type of Business Operated, Period in Business Operation, and Number of Employees. The R^2 value of 0.556 indicates that approximately 55.6% of the variation in repayment challenges can be explained by the three independent variables. The Adjusted R^2 value of 0.537 suggests that the model is moderately robust.

The ANOVA table shows that the regression model is statistically significant, indicating that the independent variables collectively explain a significant portion of the variation in repayment challenges. Specifically, the type of business operated is negatively related to repayment challenges, suggesting that certain types of businesses face fewer repayment challenges. In contrast, the period in business operation is positively related to repayment challenges, suggesting that businesses operating for longer periods face more repayment challenges.

4.5 Discussion of Results

4.5.1 Demographic information of respondents

The demographic information of the study reveals interesting insights about the respondents. The majority of respondents (65%) are male, while 35% are female, indicating a male-dominated sample. The age distribution shows that most respondents (35%) fall within the 41-50 years' age range, followed by those above 50 years (23%), indicating an older demographic.

Regarding marital status, the majority of respondents (57.3%) are married, which is consistent with a study by Reynolds et al. (2002) who found that married individuals are more likely to start and sustain businesses due to family support.

In terms of education, the majority of respondents (37.3%) have completed secondary education, which is consistent with a study by Unger et al. (2011) who found that entrepreneurs often have moderate levels of education.

4.5.2 To examine microfinance financial institutions impact on the growth of SMEs

The study's findings on accessibility and utilization of microfinance services in Kalingalinga, Zambia, reveal a complex landscape. While 76% of respondent's access microfinance services, the majority (57) rely on Microfinance Banks and informal lending groups. However, accessing credit remains challenging, with 46.7% finding it difficult or very difficult.

These findings align with existing literature, which highlights the importance of proximity to MFIs (Kumar & Mishra, 2020) and financial literacy (Rhyne, 2012) in determining loan uptake. The study also echoes concerns about institutional rigidity, lack of collateral, and poor credit history as significant barriers to access (Makina & Malobola, 2017; Olowe et al., 2013).

In Zambia, the microfinance sector is characterized by a mix of formal and informal institutions, with varying degrees of regulation and oversight (Bank of Zambia, 2023). The country's financial inclusion strategy aims to increase access to financial services, particularly for SMEs and rural communities (Zambia Microfinance Association, 2023).

However, challenges persist, including limited financial infrastructure, high interest rates, and limited financial literacy among borrowers (Tembo & Mulenga, 2019). To address these issues, MFIs must adapt their services to local needs, investing in financial literacy programs and simplifying procedures to increase accessibility.

4.5.3 To assess the accessibility and utilization of microfinance services to SMEs in Kalingalinga

This study examines the impact of microfinance financial institutions on the growth of SMEs in Kalingalinga, Zambia. The findings reveal a complex landscape, with 53.3% of respondents reporting business growth after accessing microfinance services. The most common areas of growth were sales/revenue increase (18.7%) and profitability improvement (10.7%).

However, 46.7% of respondents reported no growth, suggesting that microfinance services may not be having the desired effect for a significant proportion of respondents. The study also highlights challenges such as institutional rigidity, lack of collateral, and poor credit history as significant barriers to access.

These findings align with existing literature, which highlights the importance of proximity to MFIs (Kumar & Mishra, 2020) and financial literacy (Rhyne, 2012) in determining loan uptake. The study also echoes concerns about high interest rates and limited financial infrastructure in Zambia (Tembo & Mulenga, 2019).

Compared to previous studies, the findings of this study are consistent with global evidence that microfinance can support SME growth, but its effectiveness depends on context. Factors such as loan size, repayment terms, interest rates, and client support services influence the degree to which microfinance contributes to business expansion.

In Zambia, the study highlights the need for MFIs to adopt more flexible lending criteria, considering the socio-economic realities of borrowers and their businesses. The study also emphasizes the importance of financial literacy and entrepreneurship training in enhancing the effectiveness of microfinance interventions.

Overall, the study suggests that microfinance can be a viable tool for SME growth in Zambia, but its impact is contingent upon a supportive environment, financial literacy, and adaptable lending practices.

4.4 To identify the key challenges and determine the extent to which Microfinance institutions contributes to SMEs outcomes in terms of revenue growth, job creation, and business expansion

The study's findings on the challenges and perceptions of microfinance services in Kalingalinga, Zambia, reveal a complex landscape. The majority of respondents (68%) feel that MFI loans put pressure on their business operations, indicating that loan repayment obligations may be straining their business finances. High interest rates (37.3%), short repayment periods (21.3%), and small loan sizes (21.3%) are significant challenges faced by respondents.

These findings are consistent with global evidence that highlights the importance of transparency, fair interest rates, and flexible repayment terms in shaping borrower perceptions (Vega and Tejerina, 2019; CGAP, 2021). The study's results also echo concerns

about over-indebtedness and the need for MFIs to balance effective loan recovery strategies with empathetic customer relations (Enoch et al., 2021).

In Zambia, previous studies have shown that MFIs play a crucial role in providing financial services to underserved populations, but challenges persist (Musona and Kabwe, 2022; Banda, 2021). The current study's findings suggest that MFIs may need to reconsider their loan terms, including interest rates and repayment schedules, to make their services more accessible and manageable for borrowers.

Compared to previous studies, the findings of this study suggest that MFIs in Zambia may need to adopt more flexible lending criteria, considering the socio-economic realities of borrowers and their businesses. The study's results also emphasize the need for MFIs to invest in financial literacy programs and improve their customer relations to enhance borrower satisfaction and trust. Overall, the study's findings suggest that microfinance services can be a viable tool for SMEs growth in Zambia, but their impact is contingent upon a supportive environment, financial literacy, and adaptable lending practices.

5. Recommendation and Conclusion

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the impact of microfinance financial institutions on the growth of SMEs in Kalingalinga, Zambia, revealing a complex landscape. While 53.3% of respondents reported business growth after accessing microfinance services, 46.7% reported no growth, highlighting the need for MFIs to adapt their services to local needs. The study highlights challenges such as high interest rates, short repayment periods, and small loan sizes, which are consistent with global evidence emphasizing the importance of transparency, fair interest rates, and flexible repayment terms. The findings suggest that microfinance can be a viable tool for SME growth in Zambia, but its impact is contingent upon a supportive environment, financial literacy, and adaptable lending practices.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. MFIs should reconsider their loan terms: MFIs should review their interest rates, repayment schedules, and loan sizes to make their services more accessible and manageable for borrowers.
2. Invest in financial literacy programs: MFIs should invest in financial literacy programs to enhance borrowers' financial knowledge and management skills.
3. Improve customer relations: MFIs should improve their customer relations to enhance borrower satisfaction and trust.
4. Adopt flexible lending criteria: MFIs should adopt more flexible lending criteria, considering the socio-economic realities of borrowers and their businesses.
5. Leverage technology: MFIs should leverage technology, such as mobile banking and digital platforms, to increase accessibility and convenience for borrowers.
6. Provide entrepreneurship training: MFIs should provide entrepreneurship training to enhance borrowers' business skills and increase their chances of success.
7. Monitor and evaluate: MFIs should regularly monitor and evaluate their services to identify areas for improvement and ensure that they are meeting the needs of their clients.

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